

THERMAL DEGRADATION STUDY OF BISMALEIMIDE COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

This study evaluates the thermal and oxidative stability of a specific polymer composite. A TGA/FTIR combined technique was employed to characterize this polymer/graphite fiber composite. The polymer composite sample was pyrolyzed in nitrogen, air and 2% oxygen atmosphere, respectively, in a Perkin-Elmer thermo-gravimetric analyzer. The use of a gas-cell Fourier transform IR spectrometer downstream from the TGA allowed for the identification of the evolved gas products, the thermal oxidative stability (TOS) of this composite was compared to its thermal stability; also, comparison of the TOSs in different atmospheres is presented. In addition, the effects of specimen geometry in terms of sample thickness and surface area to volume ratio (A/V) were investigated and are discussed by relating gas diffusion into the specimen to its relative stability.

1 INTRODUCTION

Aircraft applications of high temperature composites require suitable mechanical properties at a high heating rate (100-230 °C/min) and moderate duration (10-30min) near or above their glass transition temperature (T_g). The thermal oxidative stability (TOS) in an advanced composite was an important material selection consideration for aircraft applications. In this study, the TOS of a bismaleimide (BMI) composite was investigated by dynamic thermo-gravimetric gas-cell FTIR analysis [1]. The TOS was determined in terms of weight loss characteristics and evolved gas products. The difference in the TOS in nitrogen (N_2), air and in 2% oxygen (O_2) was reported. The sample size effect on TOS was also examined and was discussed.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

The BMI resin includes two components. Component A is N, N'-bismaleimido-4, 4'-diphenylmethane (BDM) and was commercially obtained from Hubei Fengguang Chemical Factory, China. The molecular weight of BDM is 358.36 g/mole with a melting point of approximately 157 °C. The BDM consisted of a fine, yellow powder at room temperature with a purity of greater than 98%wt and contained no free aniline. Component B is 1, 4-dihydroxybenzene (DDB) supplied by Beijing Chemical agents Co., China. The molecular weight of DDB is 110.11 g/mole with a melting point of approximately 172 °C with a purity of greater than 99%wt. All chemicals were used as received without further purification. In addition to using the formulation of BMI resin (see Fig.1) with a prepolymer Mw of about 1900 (abbreviated as BMI). In processing the BMI/DDB copolymers, a powder melt technique was utilized to prepare the constituents prior to molding [5].

Prepregs of these experimental prepolymers were prepared by dissolving the respective reactants in acetone and used to impregnate T-300 graphite fibers. The solvent was allowed to evaporate, yielding prepregs with solid content of about 50 %.

2.2 Laminate Cure

The Laminates were obtained by laying up 8-ply of the respective prepregs, each ply measuring 300mm by 300mm, placed in a vacuum bag and cured in a heated press at 300°C for 6 h. The panels were then post-cured in an air-circulating oven at 300°C for an additional 12 h.

2.3 Thermogravimetric analyzer/Fourier transforms infrared spectrometer

Thermal exposure was carried out in a Thermogravimetric Analyzer (TGA) Instruments Model Pyris 1 from PerkinElmer with a quartz furnace and platinum (Pt) pan was used to heat and weigh the composite samples. In order to simulate high speed flight conditions, temperature programs of 150°C /min heating rate to isothermal temperatures of 350°C for 180 minutes were used to heat the composite samples in nitrogen, air, and 2% oxygen. The TGA microbalance was purged with an air flow of 70 ml/min and the furnace with 30 ml/min (total flow of 100 ml/min).

A Perkin-Elmer 1650 FTIR, coupled with the TGA/DTA instrument by a connecting heated gas line (an insulated Teflon tube, its temperature being about 200°C) monitored the evolved gases. A thermocouple controller maintained the gas cell temperature at about 200°C to prevent condensation.

2.4 Sample dimensions

Composite test samples of varying thickness and surface area to volume ratio (A/V) were employed for sample size effect assessment. Table 1 lists the various sample dimensions used. Test samples were pre-dried for about four days at 100°C, with daily weighing until constant sample weights were attained.

Sample Number	Dimensions L x W x T [mm]	A/V
1	2 x 2 x 2	3
2	2 x 2 x 1.8	3.1
3	2 x 2 x 1.6	3.3
4	2 x 2 x 1.4	3.4
5	2 x 2 x 1.2	3.7
6	2 x 2 x 1	4

Table.1 The dimensions of the samples

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Thermogravimetric Analyzer

As can be seen in Figure 1, in the N₂ atmosphere, after an initial drop in weight early in the isothermal hold, a linear decrease in weight occurs during the first 60 minutes, after which the rate of weight loss decreases, the weight of BMI/T300 was relatively constant throughout the 60 to 80 minutes of the test. As expected, the rate of weight loss increases from 90 minutes to the end of the test. The test resulted in the greatest weight loss rate at the first 60 minutes of the test, exhibiting the 0.6% of weight loss. However, it is notable that none of the test resulted in a weight loss greater than 1.1% in a nitrogen environment. Additionally, 90% of this weight loss occurred within the first 2 hours of the testing.

The initial weight loss may be attributed to water, acetone and other volatiles given off as a result of uncured low-molecular-weight monomers (ULMWM). Initially, water could have been formed in the powdered BMI resin introduced during storage. With the large surface area of a BMI powder, it is likely that not all waters and acetone were purged from the BMI resin by pre-dried method prior to the

start of the test. A small amount of ULMWMs could have been added from the processing of the BMI resin. However, without an oxygen environment to replenish them, the ULMWMs would soon be depleted, and the weight loss mechanism would cease. Another possible explanation for this weight loss is that it has nothing to do with decomposition. Instead, a small quantity of thermally unstable hydrocarbons in the BMI powder may be going through thermolysis. This type of process would be completely anaerobic. Regardless of the mechanism, the very low weight loss indicates that non-oxidative weight loss in BMI/T300 is negligible.

The second environment tested was in air atmosphere, and the results of these tests are also presented in Fig 1. As seen in Figure 1, the weight loss increases rapidly with the exposed times from 0 to 100 minutes, indicating that a steady-state condition may not have been reached. Interestingly, the data indicate the rate of weight loss is decreasing from 100 to 150 minutes. A decreasing rate of weight loss displayed by a BMI in an oxygen rich environment was also observed by Colin et al, and it indicates a depletion of substrate for the weight loss reaction in the polymer [6]. However, the rate of weight loss did not reduce to zero by the end of 180 minutes, conversely, a increasing of the weight loss rate are observed indicating that BMI/T300 had not yet reached a completely oxidized state.

The third environment tested was in 2% O₂ atmosphere, and a summary of the results of these tests are also presented in Fig 1. The curve exhibit an initial period of weight loss which is in agreement with the results of the samples in the N₂ atmosphere. The weight loss rate was the highest in the first 60 minutes. It is notable that the weight loss rate was some higher than the test in the N₂ atmosphere with the weight loss about 0.7%. As expected, the rate of weight loss rate after the initial loss decreases with increasing times. In fact, the rate of weight loss between 60 to 90 minutes was so low that the weight loss of the test specimen was only 0.1 % (from 0.7% to 0.8%). Even though it's initial weight loss from 0 to 60 minutes is the same as that in air, its weight loss rate is relatively smaller. In the end, it only lost 1.3% of its weight. Hence, this TGA run confirmed that the expected composite TOSs are greater in an air atmosphere of reduced oxygen content.

Fig.1 Weight loss during isothermal aging at 350°C

3.2 Fourier transforms infrared spectrum

At 350°C in air, the BMI/T300 composite samples started to lose weight at the beginning of the test regardless of its specific thickness or surface area to volume ratio. Its weight loss typically displayed three maximum weight change rates with respect to times. These three maxima occurred at 70 minutes, 110 minutes (as a shoulder) and 160 minutes, respectively. The corresponding weight losses are 1%, 1.3%, and 1.5%. A typical FTIR spectrum of the evolved gases from BMI/T300 at 350°C in air with IR band identification is presented in Fig 2. The evolved gas products are composed of H₂O (1683 cm⁻¹), CO₂, (2359 cm⁻¹), CO (2110 cm⁻¹), NO (1920 cm⁻¹), CH₄, (3014 cm⁻¹), and other aliphatic hydrocarbons (2969cm⁻¹) and aromatic hydrocarbons (3086 cm⁻¹) [6-8]. The evolved gas products also exhibited peak amounts at around the time of the maximum weight loss rate. For instance, the amounts of H₂O, CO₂, aliphatic hydrocarbons, and aromatic hydrocarbons given off are relatively high at the first peak time of 70 minutes.

The times at 1.5% weight loss, sample size and thickness effects determined for samples 1-6 are given in Table 2. It can be seen that the time for 1.5% weight loss increases slightly with decreasing sample thickness under 2mm and increasing sample A/V ratio below 4. The times at 1.5% weight loss follows a similar trend, and independent with the atmosphere environments. The sample size and thickness effects shown in Fig.3 are indicative of a gas-diffusion-controlled oxidation and degradation process.

In the air atmosphere, the weight losses of 1.5% with samples 1-2 have the 120 minutes and 125 minutes, respectively. Thus, the weight loss characteristics depend on the test specimen thickness and surface area to volume ratio, due to gas diffusion. The weight loss in test specimens 3-4 was measured at the 2% O₂ atmosphere. There are 163 minutes and 164 minutes at the weight loss time of 1.2%, respectively. Thus the thinnest and biggest A/V ratio, sample (No. 6) gave the longest weight loss time; again this suggests a gas-diffusion-controlled mechanism. The weight losses with samples 5-6 were measured in nitrogen. There are 164,165 minutes at the weight loss time of 1.5%, respectively. Evidently, these weight changes are independent of their sample size and geometry.

Fig.2 FTIR spectrum of evolved gases from BMI/T300 in air

Fig.3 Times vs. sample surface area to volume ratio

SampleNumber.	A/V	Thickness[mm]	Time[min]	Atmosphere
1	3	2	120	Air
2	3.1	1.8	125	Air
3	3.3	1.6	163	N ₂
4	3.4	1.4	164	N ₂
5	3.7	1.2	164	2%O ₂
6	4	1	165	2%O ₂

Table.2 Times for 1.5% weight loss at 350°C

4 CONCLUSIONS

In an air atmosphere, the TGA indicated that the weight loss characteristics depend on the test specimen thickness and surface area to volume ratio, due to gas diffusion. In nitrogen, the weight loss characteristics were observed to be independent of sample thickness and surface area to volume ratio. The TOS of this composite in the 2% oxygen atmosphere, which was applied to simulate aircraft flight environment, displayed a greater thermal oxidative stability than that in air, as expected. Gas-cell FTIR showed that the gas products were CO₂, CO, NO, H₂O, CH₄, phenol, and other aliphatic and aromatic hydrocarbons. It was interesting to note that these gas products also exhibited peak amounts of evolution at the weight-loss-rate peak times.

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